

Determination of Sodium-*N*-Alkyl/Dialkyl Dithiocarbamates by Reaction with 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl Chloride and Alkalimetric Determination of Ammonium-*N*-Aryl Dithiocarbamates

JYOTI TALEGAONKAR and K. S. BOPARAI*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010

Manuscript received 19 July 1980, revised 30 June 1981, accepted 1 October 1981

N-SUBSTITUTED dithiocarbamates can be determined by decomposing the sample with acid followed by potentiometric titration of the excess of the latter¹. The gravimetric method — determination of a dithiocarbamate as sulphate formed by oxidation with alkaline hydrogenperoxide²—is quite time consuming.

Sodium dithiocarbamates react with 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride, quantitatively.

This reaction has been utilized to develop a titrimetric procedure for their determination. A dithiocarbamate is reacted with 2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride in benzene-methanol, the excess of the latter is determined by titration against sodium methoxide³, using thymol blue as indicator.

The procedure has been tested with a selection of dithiocarbamates but it seems to be applicable to others with the exception of ammonium dithiocarbamates which can, however, be titrated directly against sodium methoxide using dimethylformamide as solvent and thymol blue as indicator.

The accuracy of the procedures is evident from standard deviations recorded in Table 1.

Procedures: Sodium dithiocarbamate (30 to 100 mg, prepared and purified according to published procedures^{4,5}, purity checked by gravimetric determination of sulphur⁶) was dissolved in about 5 ml of methanol followed by the addition of 15 ml of benzene. 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (DSC), in excess, was introduced. The solution was kept for 30 min before it was titrated against *ca* 0.1*N* sodium methoxide⁶, using thymol

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SODIUM-*N*-ISOBUTYLAMINO DITHIOCARBAMATE

Dithiocarbamate taken mg	DSC added mg	Titre* ml	Dithiocarbamate found mg	% Recovery
34.2	152.6	6.56	34.10	99.71
57.1	177.1	6.14	56.94	99.72
95.2	253.2	7.61	95.10	99.90

* 0.0688*M* NaOCH₃ used.

blue (3 drops, 0.3% in methanol) as indicator, to a distinct brown colour.

An ammonium dithiocarbamate (50 to 100 mg) was dissolved in 25 ml of dimethylformamide followed by titration against *ca* 0.1*N* sodium methoxide, using thymol blue indicator (3 drops, 0.3% in methanol), to a distinct blue colour stable for about 45 second. Complete data for the determination of one of the dithiocarbamates is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF DITHIOCARBAMATES

No. ^b	R,R'	Weight range mg	Average ^a recovery %	Standard deviation
1.	Methyl, H	40-90	93.67(3)	0.08
2.	<i>n</i> -Propyl, H	30-100	99.76(3)	0.10
3.	<i>iso</i> -Propyl, H	30-100	99.75(3)	0.06
4.	<i>iso</i> -Butyl, H	30-100	99.73(3)	0.11
5.	<i>P</i> -Oxydiethyl	30-100	99.72(3)	0.07
6.	Pentamethylene	30-100	99.76(3)	0.06
7.	Phenyl, H	40-150	99.87(4)	0.06
8.	4-Ethoxyphenyl, H	50-150	99.84(3)	0.10
9.	4-Chlorophenyl, H	90-100	99.87(3)	0.08

a. Figures in parentheses represent number of determination.
b. 1 to 6 are sodium salts, 7 to 9 are ammonium salts.

Acknowledgement

Laboratory facilities provided by Prof. M. M. Bokadia and the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to (J. T.) by C. S. I. R. are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. A. HULANICKI and L. SHISHKOVA, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 485.
2. C. L. WILSON and D. W. WILSON, "Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry", Vol. IB, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1960, p. 734.
3. N. KHANNA and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 1072.
4. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. IV, D. Van Nostrand, New York, 1948, p. 77.
5. A. I. VOGL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", English Language Book Society, London, 1948, p. 643.
6. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAFARIK, "Titrations in Non-aqueous Solvents", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1965, p. 99.